

EN 111 – Engineering Practice and Sustainability **Greening Engineering**

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My Sustainability Action
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Article Info

Lecturer: Dr. Mirzi Betasolo
This essay covers SDG numbers 1, 4 & 5 from the context of Mechanical Engineering

Acronyms

PNG – Papua New Guinea
SDG – Sustainable Development Goal

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Quality Education Leads to No Poverty and Gender Equality

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Introduction

The literary is a deliverable of the class EN111, Engineering Practice & Sustainability under the class of Dr Mirzi Betasolo of the School of Civil Engineering. The literature contains five Sustainable Development Goals: 1, 4 & 5

Keywords: Sustainability, Engineering Practice, Poverty, Quality Education, Gender Equality

TITLE: NO POVERTY (SDG#1)

*No poverty, everyone's happy
Where food and water is in their reach
No one can be hungry nor feel thirsty
At least that's what the news will preach
A dream like this turned into a vision
And now it's the world mission.*

*The world is struggling with poverty
And filled with hungry children everywhere
some even victims of warfare.
Mothers giving birth to future leaders
Who might just die in random sieges
Without making history.*

*No poverty, a world free of misery
With the help being both the rich and the governments,
avoiding robbery
Giving jobs and food and water
To start people off so they don't wander
No cry caused by hunger
Less number of people left to plunder
People with plenty can give to those in need,
At least enough to say they have done a good deed.
Help a person out of compassion
And you just might find a companion.*

*No poverty, a world of bliss
Where every soul finds eternal peace.
To make this happen we come together
Everyone with one agenda
No one struggles, no one goes hungry
In a world where there is plenty
No one suffers from malnutrition
No one forced to live in exclusion
We work together to remove poverty*

*And help people whose lives are in jeopardy
Saving lives in the process
And let stories be written of this success.*

*No poverty, goals are achieved
By children whose dreams were not believed
For example, a women being an engineer
As the dawn of a new era is near
An era where love and kindness prevails
With no criticism on engineers who are females.
Without barriers and limitations
The mission is accomplished with no complications.*

*No poverty, dreams and hopes are unravelling
Those of little girls and boys who saw them as very challenging
One must at least try to see things through,
As they say, 'opportunities comes only once' and that is true.
With determined children who only want success
They too will later help in this mission's progress
So we must stop poverty and stop it now Make our future
selves look back and say 'wow'.*

TITLE: QUALITY EDUCATION (SDG#4)

*Education now, is a powerful tool
Yet misused and denied by fools
With every passing year
It becomes clear
The influence of education
Elevates a nation*

*Education can change a person's perspective
Like looking at women engineers as a change that's positive
Education is the sole foundation
Upon which every woman must stand, as confirmation
That women too shall become engineers
To achieve their individual endeavours.*

*In a world where education is a right
Any child, can reach for stars shining bright
Knowledge is bestowed upon a child by a teacher,
but understanding can come to any one true reader*

In

*classrooms so bright and vibrant
Always silent as though it's vacant
Students receive the right information
Where there is no distraction.*

*Looking at the new day that's dawning
The quality of education is changing
Where technology is not a luxury
But a tool for all to use
Where access is universal
And innovation becomes a fuse*

*Imagine a world where learning is not a task
A road to freedom un-masked
Discovering the world of engineering
And finding it to be quite fascinating
Learning the math, the science, the art
Of building bridges and planes that dart
As for a world with quality education
It can save its own population*

*By sustaining and improving today's learning techniques
Allowing children in the primary level to learn basic physics
From machines that run with speed and precision
To systems that help in medical decision
It all depends on the teaches delivery
Because the child's mind could still be blurry.*

*Oh education and all its wonder
The word sounds simple but makes brain the ponder
If not upgraded to its best quality now
even a grown adult
will look at simple mechanisms
and say wow.*

TITLE: GENDER EQUALITY (SDG#4)

*Gender equality, brings us together,
In a world where we have to rely on each other,
To live and lean and love one another,
We first must make gender equality popular.*

*In a world where gender divides us,
Where roles and expectations are unjust,
Women struggle to break through,
To fields and careers that deemed untrue,
Engineering, a world of innovations and design,
A place where women should shine.*

*So women are not stared at in shock,
By those who likes to always mock,
Now all must consider this issue and talk,
So women engineers will be free to walk,*

*Instead of having people staring like a hawk,
Always in disbelief and makes women feel a little awk.*

*If women are engineers,
Helping out to be breadwinners,
Without societal norms and biases holding them back,
Nothing will be difficult for them to track,
Because by then equality would reign,
And women will not be held back by chains.*

*In a world where gender is not a problem,
Everyone will clearly fathom,
That opportunities should not be based on gender,
But on skill, talent and hard work's splendour,
So if a woman's dream is to be an engineer,
Everyone must support and not interfere.*

*For women engineers can change the world,
With their talent, passion and courage unfurled,
Let us support and empower them to thrive,
And make the engineering world come alive.*